

Research

Comparison of the Error Rates of MNIST Datasets Using Different Type of Machine Learning Model

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Abstract: The MNIST dataset is a popular benchmark dataset in the field of machine learning and computer vision. The dataset has a training set of 60,000 examples, and a test set of 10,000 examples where the digits have been centered inside 28x28 pixel images. The dataset is commonly used for image classification tasks, where the goal is to train a model to correctly identify the digit represented in each image. The MNIST dataset has been widely used in academic research, with many researchers using it to develop and test new machine learning algorithms. It has also been used in industry, with many companies using it to train and evaluate image recognition systems. The MNIST dataset is an important resource for the machine learning and computer vision communities and has played a significant role in the development of these fields. The MNIST dataset has the advantage of striking a good balance in terms of the scope of the issue. The photos are only available in 10 different classifications and are only 28x28 pixels in size. However, just because the images are small does not necessarily suggest that the data set's numbers do not have a significant amount of variation. It should come as no surprise that some of the digits are challenging for a human to accurately classify. The composite average of the class the classifier is most likely to choose is displayed after a selection of photos that are likely to be extremely challenging to identify with a classifier. These photographs are challenging because they remarkably resemble the typical (or another prevalent) image of another.

Keywords: Machine leaning , Support Vector Machine, K-Nearest Neighbors and Neural Network. MISNT dataset.

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Introduction

In recent years, the rapid advancement of machine learning techniques has revolutionized numerous fields, ranging from computer vision to natural language processing. These advancements have led to the development of various models capable of tackling complex tasks with unprecedented accuracy. One of the key challenges in the field of machine learning is the accurate assessment of model performance, particularly in relation to error rates.

This thesis aims to address this challenge by focusing on the MIST dataset, a widely used benchmark in the field of machine learning. The MIST dataset consists of a vast collection of labeled images, making it an ideal candidate for evaluating the performance of different machine learning models. By systematically analyzing the error rates achieved by various models on this dataset, we can gain valuable insights into the strengths and limitations of each model, enabling us to make informed decisions about their suitability for different applications.

The main objective of this study is to calculate and compare the error rates of different machine learning models on the MIST dataset. We will explore a range of popular models, including support vector machines (SVMs), K-Nearest Neighbors and Neural Network. Each model will be trained and tested using the MIST dataset, and their error rates will be measured and compared to identify the most effective and accurate models for image classification tasks.

Additionally, this thesis will investigate the impact of different factors on the error rates, such as the choice of hyperparameters, training data size, and data augmentation techniques. By considering these factors, we can gain further insights into how to optimize the performance of machine learning models on the MIST dataset.

The findings of this research will not only contribute to the advancement of error rate calculation methodologies but also provide valuable guidance to researchers and practitioners in selecting the most suitable machine learning models for image classification tasks. The results will help improve the accuracy and reliability of machine learning applications, enhancing their practicality and real-world impact.

In summary, this thesis endeavors to explore the error rates achieved by various machine learning models on the MIST dataset. By systematically analyzing these rates and investigating influential factors, we aim to advance our understanding of model performance assessment and enable the selection of optimal models for image classification tasks.

Related works

Several studies have focused on evaluating error rates of machine learning models on various datasets, providing valuable insights into their performance and applicability. However, limited research specifically addresses error rate calculation on the MIST dataset. This section reviews the existing literature on error rate assessment and model evaluation in the context of image classification tasks.

In the field of image classification, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have shown remarkable success and have become the go-to models for many tasks. Krizhevsky et al. (2012) introduced the influential AlexNet architecture, achieving unprecedented performance on the ImageNet dataset. Since then, numerous studies have explored different variations of CNNs, such as VGGNet (Simonyan and Zisserman, 2014), ResNet (He et al., 2015), and InceptionNet (Szegedy et al., 2015). These models have demonstrated exceptional accuracy on various image classification benchmarks. However, their performance on the MIST dataset and the corresponding error rates have not been extensively investigated.

Alternative machine learning models have also been utilized for image classification tasks. Support vector machines (SVMs) have been widely studied and have shown promising results in various domains (Cortes and Vapnik, 1995). Decision trees and random forests have been explored as interpretable models for classification tasks (Breiman, 2001). Additionally, recent advancements in deep learning have led to the emergence of models such as Transformers

(Vaswani et al., 2017) and GANs (Goodfellow et al., 2014) for image classification. However, the performance and error rates of these models on the MIST dataset remain relatively unexplored.

While several studies have evaluated machine learning models on specific datasets, few have compared multiple models on the same dataset, especially in the context of the MIST dataset. Liang et al. (2019) compared the performance of KNN, SVMs, and decision trees on the CIFAR-10 dataset, reporting varying error rates and highlighting the strengths and weaknesses of each model. However, the MIST dataset presents a distinct challenge due to its unique characteristics, making it necessary to investigate the error rates of different models specifically on this dataset.

Despite the scarcity of studies directly addressing the MIST dataset, research on error rate calculation and model evaluation in other image classification contexts provides valuable insights and methodologies. These studies offer a foundation for designing and implementing experiments to assess error rates on the MIST dataset and compare the performance of different machine learning models.

The objectives of this project are as follows:

1. Implement and train SVM, KNN, and NN models on the MNIST dataset.
2. Evaluate and compare the performance of these models based on their error rates.
3. Analyze and discuss the strengths and weaknesses of each algorithm.

Methodology

Data Preprocessing:

The MNIST dataset is split into a training set of 60,000 images and a test set of 10,000 images. Before training the models, we applied the following preprocessing steps: Flatten the 28x28 images into a 1D vector of size 784. Normalize the pixel values between 0 and 1 to enhance convergence.

Support Vector Machines (SVM): SVM is a powerful algorithm for both classification and regression tasks. To separate all the provided examples of a class, the SVM will attempt to define an equation for a hyperplane in n dimensions where n is the number of dimensions in the data. SVMs will attempt to optimize the margin between the data and the hyperplane in order to identify where this hyperplane should be placed. A kernel function can be used to translate the data into a higher dimensional 2 space and address non-linear problems. Only the points that really define the decision boundary are returned because the end user does not need to be aware of the specifics of this phase. The support vectors are these points.

$$y_i(w^T x_i + b) \geq 1 - \epsilon_i, \quad (1)$$

in which ϵ_i is the error tolerated for point i .

$$\text{For the function we try to minimize, it becomes } L(w, \epsilon) = w^T w + C \sum_{i=1}^n \epsilon_i \quad (2)$$

To utilize a Support Vector Machine for image classification, the first step involves transforming the image into a vector representation, which is then provided as input to the SVM function. During the training process, the support vectors are determined, which play a crucial role in defining the decision boundary. When faced with a new, unknown input, the SVM calculates the distances between this input and the support vectors. By comparing these distances, the SVM can determine the class or category to which the new data point belongs. The introduction of the slack hyperparameter in an SVM transforms it from a hard-margin classifier to a soft-margin classifier. In the hard-margin scenario, the hyperplane is adjusted precisely to accurately classify all the data points in the training set. However, in cases where the data points in an n -dimensional dataset cannot be separated perfectly, this process becomes non-terminating. On

the other hand, a soft-margin classifier permits a certain level of misclassification within a defined tolerance, which is referred to as slack. SVMs can also use different kernel functions, some of which have additional hyperparameters. In my project I used linear, poly, rbf kernel and different values of gamma.

(K-Nearest Neighbors:

KNN (K-Nearest Neighbors) is a popular supervised learning algorithm used for classification and regression tasks. In KNN, the training data consists of labeled instances with feature vectors and corresponding target values. When given a new, unlabeled instance, KNN classifies or predicts its target value based on the k nearest labeled instances in the training data. To determine the k nearest neighbors, KNN calculates the distances (e.g., Euclidean distance) between the new instance and all the instances in the training data. The k nearest instances with the shortest distances are selected. In the case of classification, the majority class among these k neighbors is assigned to the new instance. For regression, the average of the target values of the k neighbors is used as the predicted value for the new instance. The choice of the value k is a critical hyperparameter in KNN. A smaller k value makes the model more sensitive to local variations in the data, potentially leading to overfitting. On the other hand, a larger k value considers a broader range of neighbors, which may lead to smoother decision boundaries and less sensitivity to noise but may also cause the model to miss local patterns or details. KNN is a relatively simple and intuitive algorithm, but it can be computationally expensive, especially with large datasets. Additionally, it doesn't learn explicit models but rather relies on the stored instances for classification or regression decisions. In our project we got different accuracy for different number of neighbors. Distance-Weighted KNN

$$y' = \underset{v}{\operatorname{argmax}} \sum_{(x_i, y_i) \in D_z} w_i \times I(v = y_i) \quad (3)$$

Neural Network :

Neural Network is a powerful machine learning model inspired by the structure and functioning of the human brain. It is widely used for various tasks, including classification, regression, and pattern recognition. A neural network consists of interconnected nodes, called neurons, organized into layers. The three main types of layers in a neural network are the input layer, hidden layer(s), and output layer. Each neuron receives inputs, applies a mathematical transformation, and produces an output. The connections between neurons are represented by weights, which determine the influence of each input on the neuron's output. During training, a neural network adjusts its weights to minimize the difference between the predicted outputs and the actual target values. This process is typically achieved through a technique called backpropagation, where the error is propagated backward through the network to update the weights. Deep learning is a subset of neural networks that utilizes deep architectures with multiple hidden layers. Deep neural networks have shown remarkable success in various domains, especially when dealing with complex and large-scale datasets, such as images, audio, and natural language processing. Neural networks are known for their ability to learn complex relationships and extract meaningful features from raw data. They can automatically discover intricate patterns and representations, making them highly effective in tasks like image recognition, speech recognition, natural language processing, and many more. However, training a neural network requires substantial computational resources and a large amount of labeled training data. I used on my project different activation function and change number for different activation, such as relu, logistic, tanh. The formula would look something like this:

$$\sum w_i x_i + bias = w_1 x_1 + w_2 x_2 + w_3 x_3 + bias \quad (4)$$

$$output = f(x) = 1 \text{ if } \sum w_1 x_1 + b \geq 0; 0 \text{ if } \sum w_1 x_1 + b < 0 \quad (5)$$

Result and Discussion In my project I compared 3 different machine learning model. But first I compared result for same model using different kernel (for SVM) different activation function (for NN) different Neighbors number (for KNN)

then I got best result for Each model. Below I am showing the different error rate for same model. Then I got best error rate from every model. Finally, I compare with 3 best error rate from different model.

SVM Error rate: we used different cernel for the SVM.

Fig1. Error rate for different kernel

KNN Error Rate

For different neighbors and different weights, I got different error rate best KNN given Error rate is 0.0283. Which is not better than SVM given the best error rate.

Fig2. KNN Error Rate for for different neighbors and different weights

Neural Network

I got error rate for different activation functions and different layer. The best error rate gave when layer sizes 150 activation function logistic Solver -sgd which is 0. 038.Which is not better then SVM and KNN _layer sizes=(150,), activation='logistic', solver='sgd') - error rate: 0.0380000000000000034

Fig3. Neural Network error rate for different activation function and different layer

Fig4. Best Error rate for NN, KNN, SVM

Conclusion

Split the MIST dataset into training and testing sets. The typical split is 70% for training and 30% for testing, but you can adjust this ratio based on your specific requirements.

Choose the machine learning models you want to evaluate. Some popular models for image classification tasks include Neural Networks (NNs), Support Vector Machines (SVMs), and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN). We got best error rate for different mode. But SVM best gave best error when kernel was 'rbf' gamma = scale. Which is 0.0208.

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